

Energy Planning for Ethiopia's Agro-Industrial Growth Using Energy Access Explorer

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 3. Energy Access Explorer (EAE)
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Executive Summary:

This study investigates energy access strategies to support Ethiopia's agro-industrial development, focusing on Rural Transformation Centres (RTCs) linked to Integrated Agro-Industrial Parks (IAIPs). Using the Energy Access Explorer tool, spatial analysis was conducted to evaluate three pathways: connection to existing grid infrastructure, solar energy potential, and wind energy potential. Results show that while seven RTCs are located within 5 KM of distribution substations, lack of data on substation load capacity and RTC energy demand poses challenges to grid integration.

Additionally, ten RTCs were identified as suitable for clean energy deployment, based on solar irradiance and wind speed thresholds. The analysis highlights the urgent need to improve energy reliability for RTC functionality and scale-up. Policy recommendations include prioritizing infrastructure upgrades, expanding decentralized solar and wind systems, and integrating RTC energy planning into national strategies. Further field assessments and improved data access will be essential to support investment and implementation in Ethiopia's rural energy transition.

1. Introduction:

The Government of Ethiopia has prioritized the development of agro-processing industries as a pathway to enhance rural livelihoods, increase agricultural productivity, and support inclusive economic growth (Farmonaut, 2024). As part of this initiative, the establishment of Rural Transformation Centres (RTCs) within a 100-kilometer radius of Integrated Agro-Industrial Parks (IAIPs) has been proposed (UNIDO, 2016). These RTCs are envisioned to serve as localized hubs where agricultural produce is collected, semi-processed, and then transported to the IAIPs for further value addition (EIC, n.d.). The main aim of the RTCs is to reduce post-harvest losses, create rural employment, and integrate smallholder farmers into larger value chains (Tigabu et al., 2024).

However, a critical challenge impeding the effective operation of RTCs is the lack of reliable energy sources, which limits the use of modern processing and storage technologies (Kumssa et al., 2022). While there are broader systemic challenges, this study focuses specifically on the energy dimension.

Using the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) tool, this research aims to:

- map the geographical distribution of IAIPs and associated RTCs, and
- evaluate existing and potential off-grid renewable energy options—specifically solar and wind—to sustainably power these centers.

2. Methodology:

This study employed a spatial, multi-criteria analysis approach using the EAE tool to assess the feasibility of connecting RTCs in Ethiopia to either existing grid infrastructure or clean energy alternatives such as solar and wind. The analysis involved integrating demand-side indicators—such as population density, crop and livestock productivity, and RTC locations—with supply-side data including solar irradiance, wind speed, and proximity to distribution substations and lines. Layers were selected, filtered, and weighted to generate composite spatial outputs that helped prioritize RTCs for potential energy access solutions.

Spatial datasets were obtained from publicly available global and regional sources.

- Population data (Bondarenko et al., 2020),
- Administrative boundaries (Humanitarian Data Exchange),
- IAIP and RTC locations (UNIDO, 2016),
- Crop productivity (You et al., 2017),
- Livestock density (Gilbert et al., 2018)
- Distribution substations (EEU, 2020; MoWIE, 2020),
- Distribution lines (EEU, 2020; MoWIE, 2020),
- Wind speed (World Bank Group and DTU, 2024),
- Global horizontal Irradiation (World Bank Group and Solargis, 2024)

The key methodological process followed in this study, along with selected steps undertaken at each stage, is outlined below (Mentis et al., 2019).

Figure: EAE methodology and steps

3. Results:

As part of Ethiopia's national industrialization strategy, the Government has established four IAIPs, located in Oromia, Amhara, Tigray, and the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region (SNNPR) (UNIDO, 2016). These parks are strategically designed to stimulate agro-industrial development while fostering inclusive rural transformation.

Figure: Integrated Agro-Industrial Parks (IAIPs)

The above map shows the locations of Ethiopia's four main IAIPs, each with a 100-kilometre radius designated for supporting Rural Transformation Centres (RTCs). Within these combined areas, approximately 28.77 million people reside across 102,202 square kilometres.

In line with the IAIP model, each park is planned to be supported (or in some cases, is currently supported) by multiple RTCs situated within a 100-kilometer radius to facilitate efficient produce aggregation and processing (UNIDO, 2016). Some RTCs are already operational, undertaking key activities such as post-harvest handling, primary processing, cold storage, and logistical

coordination (World Bank, 2022). Others are at various stages of development, reflecting a phased implementation strategy (Ministry of Agriculture, 2023).

Figure: 4 IAIPs and their corresponding RTCs (26 in total)

In alignment with the RTC development plan, these centres are strategically located near areas with high agricultural productivity and significant livestock density, as demonstrated by the analysis below.

Figure: RTC locations concentrated in areas with high population density, elevated crop productivity, and livestock presence

Three models of power delivery were explored for integrating RTCs into the energy system.

Existing Infrastructure Assessment:

In the first model, existing grid infrastructure near RTC sites was assessed based on proximity. A 5-kilometre radius was used as the threshold—only distribution substations or lines within this distance were considered, to help minimize transmission losses. Based on this criterion, approximately seven RTCs were identified as potentially connectable to the existing grid infrastructure.

Although 33 kV distribution lines—typically suitable for industrial use—were also reviewed, and many were found to pass through the mapped RTC locations, it remains unclear whether these lines can reliably supply power to the RTCs. This is because the specific power requirements of each RTC are not yet known.

A key constraint is the lack of data on both the current capacity of these substations and the expected load of the RTCs. Further assessment is required to determine whether nearby substations can accommodate the additional demand.

Figure: Proximity of distribution substations to RTCs

Solar Energy Potential Assessment:

Secondly, the Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) levels around RTC locations were analyzed to identify viable solar energy options. Areas with GHI values exceeding 2,000 kWh/m² were considered suitable for solar power deployment.

Figure: Global Horizontal Irradiation Levels (Energy access potential low to high)

Based on this analysis, nine RTC locations were identified as suitable for off-grid solar energy solutions. These areas have strong solar potential, making them appropriate for standalone renewable energy systems. Among these, the following two locations showed the highest levels of solar energy availability.

Figure: Top 2 RTCs with high energy access potential (GHI)

Wind Energy Potential Assessment

Lastly, wind speeds around RTC locations were analyzed to identify viable wind energy options. Areas with average wind speeds exceeding 3 m/s were considered suitable for small-scale wind power deployment.

Figure: Wind speed levels (Energy access potential low to high)

Based on this analysis, six RTC locations were identified as suitable for wind energy deployment. Among these, the following two sites recorded the highest average wind speeds, indicating strong potential for small-scale wind generation.

Figure: Top 2 RTCs with high wind energy potential

4. Discussion:

The development of RTCs is a cornerstone of Ethiopia's strategy to promote rural industrialization and agro-processing (Tefera and Galato, 2022). However, unlocking the full potential of RTCs depends heavily on ensuring reliable and adequate access to energy (Hassen and Degu, 2019). This section summarizes key findings from the analysis and outlines their broader implications.

Power Reliability Challenges: Even in urban settings, IAIPs experience frequent and prolonged power outages, reflecting broader issues in Ethiopia's power supply system. A study of manufacturing firms reported an average of 10.82 power outages per month, each lasting nearly 6 hours, with an average duration of 30.62 hours per month. These disruptions lead to reduced productivity, increased costs due to generator usage, equipment damage, and missed

market opportunities (Hassen and Degu, 2019). For RTCs located in more remote or underserved areas, the situation is often worse, with no guaranteed access to stable grid power. Thus, any initial assessment of energy access for RTCs must go beyond proximity and include an evaluation of grid reliability and available capacity.

Renewable Energy Potential: Ethiopia is well-positioned to leverage solar and wind energy as alternatives or supplements to grid power. The country receives high solar irradiance across much of its territory, and several regions also report wind speeds suitable for small- to medium-scale turbines. The Ethiopian government, through policies like the National Electrification Program (NEP), aims to expand renewable energy access, especially in off-grid areas. Solar and wind systems offer scalable, modular solutions that can power RTCs sustainably and independently of the national grid, reducing reliance on hydropower and enhancing climate resilience.

Based on the EAE analysis, a set of RTC locations have been identified where power connectivity could be prioritized. These include sites with either close proximity to grid infrastructure or high suitability for solar and wind-based off-grid systems. Most of the RTCs are at a distance of (0-5 KM to a 33 kV distribution line). However, these initial results should be interpreted with caution, as they are subject to limitations discussed in the following section.

As part of the Ethiopia IAIP support project, assessments were conducted for selected IAIPs and key RTCs (African Development Bank, 2018). The findings show that many planned energy connections rely on existing infrastructure. For example, Motta RTC (1.2 MVA) and Dilla RTC (1.157 MVA) were meant to be powered via existing 33 kV lines, but these connections have not fully materialized, leaving the RTCs non-operational. This highlights the importance of exploring alternative energy options. Analysis shows that 10 out of 26 RTCs have strong potential for clean energy deployment.

Integrated Agro-Industrial Park (IAIP)	Rural Transformation Centres (RTC)	Proximity: Distribution Substation	Solar Potential	Wind Potential
Bure IAIP <i>(South West Amhara region; total area: 154.99 hectares)</i>	Motta	3 KM	High (98%)	
	Merawi			
	Finote Selam	<1 KM		
	Dangila	2 KM		
	Enjibara			
	Chagni			
	Amanuel			
Yirgalem IAIP <i>(Eastern SNNP region; total area: 108.8 hectares)</i>	Dilla	5 KM		
	Yirgachefe			
	Bule			

	Daye			
	Aleta Wendo			
	Hawela Tula			
Baeker IAIP <i>(Western Tigray region; total area: 150.92 hectares)</i>	Mai Kadra		High (95%)	High (90%)
	Setit-humer	3 KM	High (96%)	
	Adigoshu		High (98%)	High (91%)
	Adi-hirdi			
	Maygaba		High (97%)	
	Dansha		High (93%)	
	Shire-Indaselassie	1 KM	High (95%)	High (91%)
Bulbula IAIP <i>(Central Eastern Oromia region; total area: 263 hectares)</i>	Shashemene	1 KM		
	Meki		High (100%)	High (91%)
	Dodola			
	Bale Robe	1 KM		
	Iteya			High (100%)
	Olanchiti		High (100%)	High (96%)

Table: Potential sources for improved energy access (10 RTCs)

Some of the **limitations** of this analysis include:

1. **Data Gaps:** The analysis was limited by the lack of access to real-time data on the load profiles of distribution substations and the actual energy needs of RTCs.
2. **Modeling Constraints:** EAE tool provides valuable geospatial insights but does not account for operational reliability, financial feasibility, or implementation capacity. It also assumes uniform availability of infrastructure and may not reflect localized constraints such as terrain or grid congestion. Some of these limitations could be addressed by complementing the analysis with tools such as OnSSET or FinPlan, which incorporate system-level modelling and financial planning.

Way Forward: Recommendations

Ensuring effective energy access for RTCs requires an integrated strategy that spans policy, technical design, and operational planning. First, national investment could focus on upgrading existing grid infrastructure to enhance reliability and load capacity, particularly in areas where grid proximity aligns with RTC locations. For more remote centres, targeted off-grid solutions could be supported using tools like EAE to identify sites where solar and wind power offer the most promise.

To facilitate implementation, Ethiopia could strengthen its renewable energy policy framework. This includes improving permitting processes, creating incentives such as feed-in tariffs and

capital subsidies, and expanding access to affordable financing for energy entrepreneurs and cooperatives. Integrating RTC energy needs into the National Electrification Program will ensure these centres are not overlooked in national planning.

Furthermore, future efforts could be informed by deeper field-level research. Site-specific energy audits are needed to establish accurate load profiles, operational needs, and consumption patterns of RTCs. Understanding the economic costs of unreliable electricity—such as post-harvest losses, equipment underutilization, or business downtime—will support better investment decisions. Research could also explore hybrid energy models and the practical barriers to off-grid deployment, including high upfront costs, lack of technical capacity, and maintenance challenges. Addressing these gaps will enhance Ethiopia's ability to implement resilient, scalable energy solutions that empower rural industries and communities.

5. Conclusion:

This study highlights the central role of energy access in operationalizing Ethiopia's RTCs, which are key to driving rural industrialization and agro-processing. Through geospatial analysis using the EAE, it was found that while several RTCs are near grid infrastructure, reliability and capacity concerns remain unresolved. Additionally, strong solar and wind energy potential was identified in 10 RTC locations, suggesting that off-grid renewable solutions can complement or substitute for traditional connections. The findings reinforce the need for integrated planning across energy, agriculture, and industrial sectors. Moving forward, the government and its partners could prioritize improving grid reliability, deploying decentralized renewable energy where feasible, and aligning RTC energy needs with national electrification plans. Targeted investments, combined with site-level energy audits and financing mechanisms, will be essential to overcoming current implementation barriers. A coordinated, data-driven approach will ensure that RTCs fulfill their intended role in Ethiopia's inclusive and sustainable development agenda.

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